

THE CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH OF NATIONAL SPECIFICITY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL SEMANTICS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the actual linguistic problem – the study of national identity of phraseological semantics in contrastive aspect. The research is carried out within the framework of contrastive methods. The contrastive analysis allows to reveal national specific patterns of phraseological units in the German language against the Russian language background.

Keywords: national identity, contrastive analysis, phraseological semantics, semantic (component) analysis of phraseological units, national specific patterns of semantics.

КОНТРАСТИВНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ И ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ СПЕЦИФИКИ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СЕМАНТИКИ

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена актуальной проблеме современной лингвистики – изучению национальной специфики фразеологической семантики в контрастивном аспекте. Исследование выполнено в рамках контрастивной методики. Контрастивный анализ позволяет выявить национально-специфические особенности семантики фразеологических единиц немецкого языка на фоне языка сопоставления (русского).

Ключевые слова: национальная специфика, контрастивный анализ, фразеологическая семантика, семантический анализ фразеологических единиц, национально-специфические черты/особенности семантики.

FRAZEOLOGIK SEMANTIKANING MILLIY XUSUSIYATLARINI KONTRASTLI TAHLIL QILISH VA O'RGANISH

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Izoh: Maqola zamonaviy tilshunoslikning dolzarb muammosiga bag'ishlangan-frazeologik semantikaning milliy xususiyatlarini qarama-qarshi tomondan o'rganish. Tadqiqot qarama-qarshi texnikaning bir qismi sifatida amalga oshirildi. Kontrastli tahlil nemis tilining frazeologik birliklari semantikasining milliy o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini taqqoslash tili (rus) fonida aniqlashga imkon beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: milliy o'ziga xoslik, kontrastli tahlil, frazeologik semantika, frazeologik birliklarning semantik tahlili, semantikaning milliy o'ziga xos xususiyatlari/xususiyatlari.

Introduction. Contrastive analysis is a method used in linguistics to compare and contrast two or more languages to identify their structural differences and similarities. When we apply this method to the concept of "face" in English and Uzbek, we can explore both the literal and metaphorical uses of the word in each language.

The growing interest in comparative and contrastive research is currently explained by the expansion of international contacts in various fields of activity and the need to effectively solve problems that inevitably arise in the process of communication and interaction of people belonging to different linguistic and cultural communities. Effective communication requires knowledge of the national-specific features of languages, which are reflected in the semantics of language units. As noted by Russian and foreign linguists engaged in the study of German phraseology, it is phraseological units that are particularly difficult both when learning a foreign language and when communicating directly with native speakers in the process of intercultural communication [2. p. 158; 7. p. 117-118]. Phraseology is becoming an actual subject of research in connection with the increased interest in the linguistic picture of the world, since it forms a bright and nationally peculiar part of the linguistic picture of the world of any people. "The phraseological composition of a language is a mirror in which a linguistic and cultural community identifies its national identity" [6. p. 9].

Phraseology is a complex and time-consuming subject of research, as

discussions continue about the very concept of a phraseological unit, about the specifics of phraseological meaning, opinions differ on the typology of phraseological units, the problem of contrastive description of the semantics of phraseological units is poorly developed. Studies in the field of national peculiarities of phraseology are etymological (A.M. Babkin, Yu. A. Gvozdev, V. I. Zimin, V. M. Mokienko, L. I. Roizenzon, A.V. Filippov, N. M. Shansky), culturological (E. M. Vereshchagin, V. G. Kostomarov, D. G. Maltseva, V. N. Telia) and ethnographic (G. D. Gachev, N. D. Markovina, Yu. A. Sorokin, N. I. Tolstoy, N. V. Ufimtseva) character, but there are few proper semantic studies of the national specificity of phraseological units in the contrastive aspect. The consideration of phraseology in the contrastive aspect is one of the new directions in linguistics, which is of increasing interest to researchers. The increased interest in contrastive linguistics is explained not only by its involvement in solving the actual theoretical problems of individual languages, but also by the fact that it is directly related to practical tasks: teaching foreign languages, theory and practice of translation, is significant for the practice of compiling bilingual dictionaries. The purpose of our work is to synchronously identify the national-specific features of the semantics of phraseological units of the German language against the background of the matching language (Russian). The study was conducted on the material of German phraseological units with names of parts of the face and their correspondences in the Russian language. They were chosen as the research material due to the fact that preliminary analysis showed the presence of noticeable national specifics of semantics in these thematic groups. We consider the structural approach to phraseological meaning as a set of semantic components of various types to be the basis and prerequisite for the implementation of a contrastive study of phraseology [4. p. 177]. Applying to the study of the semantics of phraseological units in our study the principles of describing the semantics of linguistic units developed in modern semasiology and the methodology of seminal analysis, we describe the meanings of phraseological units as a set of semes. Comparing phraseological units of different languages according to their seminal description, we identify mismatched components of meaning in the compared correspondences of the two languages. As a result of the description of the semantics of phraseological units of the German language against the background of the matching language – Russian – the national specificity of the semantics of the units of the studied language is revealed. Studies by Z. D. Popova, I. A. Sternin, I. P. Zlenko, K. Fleckenstein, etc. They allow us to conclude that the manifestation of the national specifics of the semantics of lexical and phraseological units is possible at all

language levels [1; 3; 5]. The main forms of manifestation of the national specificity of phraseological semantics, as the study showed, are: 1) semantic-figurative equivalence of phraseological units, that is, complete coincidence in meaning and phraseological image (in this case, we can talk about zero specificity); Philology 177 2) semantic equivalence of phraseological units, that is, complete coincidence in denotative, connotative, structural-linguistic components of meaning and difference in phraseological image; 3) semantic national specificity – the presence of separate seminal differences when the phraseological image coincides; 4) semantic-figurative national specificity (the presence of separate seminal inter-language differences and differences in phraseological image); 5) phraseological equivalence – the absence of a phraseological unit in one language when it is present in the language of comparison. Inter-language analysis makes it possible to identify the national specifics of phraseological units of the two languages in the seminal differences of the compared phraseological units: 1) differences in the denotative component of meaning; 2) differences in the connotative component of meaning; 3) differences in the denotative and connotative components of meaning; 4) differences in the structural and linguistic component of meaning (stylistic, territorial, temporal, social, frequency). Here are some examples. Differences in the denotative component of the value • being born with a golden/silver spoon in his mouth (letters. to be born with a gold/silver spoon in your mouth) – Rus. to be born in a shirt; in German it has a differential denotative seme "belonging to a rich family". Differences in the connotative component of the meaning to offend the eye; to be an insult to the eye (letters. to offend the eye; to be an insult to the eye) – Rus. to cut the eye; in English – ironic; in Russian – negative-emotional; • making long/pointed ears ('to listen with curiosity, to eavesdrop') – to prick up (alert) ears; in English – disapproving, mocking; in Russian – unappreciative, unemotional. Functional and stylistic differences • say something to the face Russian in person (to speak, scold, etc.); in English – interstitial, in Russian – colloquial; • burning his mouth (letters. burn your mouth, mouth) – Rus. to say (or blurt out) too much; in English – rude, in Russian – colloquial. Functional-frequency differences • [not] according to jnds. His nose (letters. to be (not) on the nose of someone-L.) – Rus. (not) to taste; in English – little-used, in Russian – common; dying on the lips (letters. to freeze at someone-L. on the lips) – Rus. words froze at someone-L. on the lips; in English – uncommon, in Russian – uncommon. Functional-temporal differences • pulling the worms out of the nose [one by one] (letters. to pull out worms from someone's nose) - Rus. to extract the whole background from someone; in English – modern, in Russian – outdated;

have a lot on your mind (letters. to have a lot behind your ears) – Rus. to get bogged down by the ears; in English – obsolete and little-used, in Russian - modern, common. The study shows that the semantic description of - phraseological correspondences between them can reveal relationships reflecting different degrees of semantic proximity. The following are distinguished: – phraseological equivalents – units that are maximally similar in composition to nuclear and peripheral semes and provide adequate translation in all contexts; – translational phraseological correspondences – units of two languages that have several common semes and are used for translation in some contexts. Phraseological equivalents are proposed to be considered phraseological units that have complete similarity in semantics and phraseological image in both languages, for example: Making eyes Rus. make big eyes; bumping into something with your nose Rus. poke someone's nose-L. into what-L.; Philology 178 to be in love over the/over both ears Rus. to fall head over heels in love. In addition, it is proposed to consider as phraseological equivalents and such phraseological correspondences, for which a complete semantic coincidence is recorded with the difference of the phraseological image. For example: don't mince words (letters. do not take a piece of paper to your mouth, 'openly express your opinion') – Rus. speak bluntly. Equivalents with a complete coincidence of images can be called semantic-figurative phraseological equivalents, equivalents with a non-matching image - semantic phraseological equivalents. A group of phraseological correspondences is distinguished, which are characterized by national specificity (the presence of separate seminal inter-language differences) and complete coincidence in phraseological image. We designate such units as units with national specifics of semantics. A group of phraseological correspondences is singled out, for which the manifestation of national specificity is recorded (the presence of separate seminal inter-language differences), as well as the difference in phraseological images. We call such units with semantic-figurative national specifics. For a contrastive description of phraseology, the number of units of the matching language that can be matched to the unit of the source language under study is essential. From this point of view, linear correspondences, vector correspondences, and the absence of phraseological correspondence in the matching language are distinguished – a phraseological lacuna [4. p. 25]. 1. To linear correspondences (ratio 1:1) for example, the following phraseological units apply: bumping into something with your nose Rus. poke someone's nose-L. in what-L. (for edification); do not see further than the nose reaches Rus. do not see further than your (or your own) nose. 2. To vector correspondences (ratio 1:N) the following phraseological units can be attributed: A.

Several units in English – one unit in Russian: 1. keep your mouth clean (letters. keep a clean mouth); 2. keep your mouth shut (mouth, face, etc.) (letters. keep your mouth shut). Russian – to keep your mouth shut – to be silent, not to talk, not to say too much; to be careful in statements. B. One unit in English – several units in Russian: living from hand to mouth. In Russian: – to survive from bread to kvass (simple) – to live very poorly, to suffer need, deprivation; – barely make ends meet – somehow cope with material difficulties; to survive, to need. 3. The lack of phraseological correspondence in the Russian language. For example: taking hold of your own nose (letters. grab your own nose) – worry about your own mistakes and weaknesses instead of criticizing others; look for and understand your mistakes (take hold of your own nose! look at yourself better!); to earn a golden nose (letters. earn a golden nose) – earn a lot of money. The absence of correspondences suggests the presence of phraseological lacunae in one of the two languages studied. A phraseological lacuna is the absence of an inter-language phraseological correspondence in one language relative to another. The phraseology of one language, represented by a lacuna in the matching language, is defined as an equivalent phraseology without. The conducted research has shown that the studied thematic group of English phraseological units against the background of the Russian language demonstrates significantly more striking semantic differences than similarities. The national-specific differences in the semantic structure of the analyzed phraseological units, revealed during the contrastive study, reflect the peculiarities of the conceptualization of the fragments of the linguistic worldview in both cultures, indicate the national identity and uniqueness of the image of the world of the English and Russian peoples.

References:

1. Zlenko, I. P. National specifics of word semantics [Text]: autoref. dis.... Candidate of Phil. sciences / I. P. Zlenko. - Voronezh, 2004. – 24 p.
2. Maltseva, D. G. Country studies through phraseological units [Text] / D. G. Maltseva. – M.: Higher School, 1991. – 173 p.
3. Popova, Z. D. Lexical system of language [Text] / Z. D. Popova, I. A. Sternin. – Voronezh: Voronezh Publishing House. University, 1984. – 148 p.
4. Sternin, I. A. Contrastive linguistics. Problems of theory and methodology of research [Text] / I. A. Sternin. - Voronezh: Istoki, 2004. - 189 p.
5. Sternin, I. A. Essays on contrastive lexicology and phraseology [Text] / I. A. Sternin, K. Fleckenstein. Russian Russian Phraseology [Text] / V. N. Telia. – M.: School "Languages of Russian Culture", 1986. - 141 p. 7. Palm, Ch. Phraseologie:

eine Einführung [Text]. – Halle: Martin Luther Halle University, 1989. – 129 p.

6. Telia, V. N. Russian Phraseology [Text] / V. N. Telia. – M.: School "Languages of Russian Culture", 1986. - 141 p.

7. Palm, Ch. Phraseologie: eine Einführung [Text] / Ch. Palm. – Tübingen: Gunter Narr Verlag, 1995. – 130 S. Dictionaries

8. Duden. Redewendungen und sprichwörtliche Redensarten. Wörterbuch der deutschen Idiomatik. Duden Bd. 11 [Text]. – Mannheim: Dudenverlag, 1992. Russian Russian Dictionary, 1980.

9 Devkin, V. D. German-Russian Dictionary of Colloquial Vocabulary [Text] / V. D. Devkin. – M.: Russian language, 1994.

10. Phraseological Dictionary of the Russian language [Text] / edited by A. I. Molotkov. – M. Russian Russian Language, 1967.

11. Phraseological dictionary of the Russian language [Text] / comp. A. N. Tikhonov, A. G. Lomov, L. A. Lomova. – M.: Higher School, 2003.

12. Phraseological Dictionary of the Russian literary language [Text] / edited by A. I. Fedorov. – M.: Topi